

This method, thus, has got considerable synthetic importance in providing an alternate and convenient route for the synthesis of aroyl cyanides without the use of external cyanide ion. Further, the easy preparation of 2-aryl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolines (3) takes the advantage of replacing the 2-pyridone derivatives as reported earlier.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a WISWO melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

2-Phenyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3a; $R^1 = C_6H_5$) and 2-benzyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3b; $R^1 = C_6H_5CH_2$) were prepared following literature procedure^{6,7}.

Reaction of 2-phenyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3a) with phenacyl bromides. Isolation of aroyl cyanides (typical procedure): A solution of phenacyl bromide (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) in DMSO (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 20 h. The aminoquinazoline (3; 1.2 g, 0.005 mol) was then added and the mixture was heated for 6 h at 100°. It was then poured after cooling into ice-water (50 ml), extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml), dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated in vacuum. The crude product was treated with benzene when a solid settled which was filtered to give 7 ($R^1 = C_6H_5$), m.p. 234° (lit.⁶ 235°). The benzene filtrate on concentration in vacuum and subsequent trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave a low melting solid of benzoyl cyanide (0.8 g, 62%), m.p. 32° (lit.⁸ 32–5°).

In a similar manner, reaction of 3 with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide gave the corresponding *p*-methylbenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 49° (lit.¹⁰ 50–2°), *p*-chlorobenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 41° (lit.¹¹ 41.0–2.5°) and *p*-nitrobenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 115–16° (lit.¹² 116°) in 70, 72 and 54% yields, respectively.

Reaction of 2-benzyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3b) with phenacyl bromides. Isolation of aroyl cyanides: The preparative procedure adopted was the same as above. The benzene insoluble product in all cases was 7 ($R^1 = C_6H_5CH_2$), m.p. 255–56° (lit.⁶ 256°). The respective yields of aroyl cyanides isolated from the benzene-petroleum ether fractions were 58, 62, 65 and 50% in case of phenacyl bromide, *p*-methylphenacyl bromide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide.

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Synthesis of Novel Types of 1,4-Oxazino- and 1,4-Pyrazino-phenazine Derivatives

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LITERATURE survey showed that 1,4-benzoxazines are associated with a wide range of biological and pharmacological properties¹⁻⁴. Various derivatives of dihydropyrazines are reported to be potent antimalarial and antibacterial agents⁵⁻⁷. Pyrazino[2,3-*b*]phenazine has been claimed to have potential action against leaf blast fungal disease⁸ in green-house. The condensed oxazines also possess fluorescent brightening property⁹. In continuation of our earlier work on fused heterocyclic systems^{10,11}, we describe here the synthesis and antibacterial and antifungal activities of the title compounds.

Various 2-aryl-(1,4)oxazino[5,6-*b*]phenazines (3) have been prepared by refluxing 2-amino-3-hydroxyphenazine^{1,2} (1) and phenacyl bromides (2) in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate. The above cyclisation in tetrahydrofuran gave low yields. The 2,3-diaminophenazine^{1,2} (4) was cyclised with phenacyl bromides (2) by refluxing them in dry acetone containing potassium carbonate to give 2-aryl-3,4-dihydro[1,4]pyrazino[5,6-*b*]phenazines (5).

All the compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data and a few have

been screened against bacteria and fungi by standard methods.

Experimental

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (90 MHz) on a Varian A-90 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JMS D-300 spectrometer at 70 eV. The physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

General procedure: A mixture of *o*-hydroxyaminophenazine or diaminophenazine (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.015 mol) in dry acetone (250 ml) was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. To the resulting suspension was added additional amount of anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.015 mol) and phenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. It was then filtered hot and the excess acetone distilled off. The residue was diluted with ice-cold water (100 ml), and the resulting solid was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to get the title compounds.

Biological screening: A few of the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity by filter paper disc technique^{1a}. The gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria employed for the tests were *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Escherichia coli*. The results are given in Table 2.

The antifungal activity was determined by the glass-slide humid chamber technique¹⁴. The fungi employed were *Dreschlera speciferum* and *Fusarium solani*. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYLOXAZINO- AND 2-ARYLDIHYDROPYRAZINO-PHENAZINES*

Compd. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %
3a	H	268	50
3b	Cl	220	48
3c	Br	249	42
3d	OH ₂	>350	39
3e	OCH ₃	>350	35
3f	NO ₂	>350	46
5a	H	138	41
5b	Cl	115	45
5c	Br	180	49
5d	OH ₂	202	41
5e	OCH ₃	251	48
5f	NO ₂	>350	44

*Elemental analyses found satisfactory.

Results and Discussion

The absence of absorptions due to free amino and hydroxy groups confirms cyclisation. The general ir bands are found at 1 600–1 590 (C=N) and 1 250–1 10) cm⁻¹ (C–N–C). The aromatic stretching vibrations are observed at 800–650 cm⁻¹. The symmetric and asymmetric stretchings of an aliphatic ether system are observed at 1 190 and 1 070 cm⁻¹. The N–H absorption for the compounds 5 is observed at 3 400–3 000 cm⁻¹.

The pmr spectra display a singlet at δ 4.0 for two methylene protons. The phenyl nucleus protons appear at δ 8.0, and the multiplet centered at δ 8.5

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF OXAZINO- AND DIHYDROPYRAZINO-PHENAZINES

Compd. no.	Concn. µg ml ⁻¹	Antibacterial (Inhibition, mm)				Concn. µg ml ⁻¹	Antifungal (% Inhibition)	
		<i>B.s.</i> (+)	<i>S.a.</i> (+)	<i>E.c.</i> (-)	<i>P.v.</i> (-)		<i>D.s.</i>	<i>F.s.</i>
3a	400	0.6	0.3	0.1	—	360	—	—
	600	1.0	0.4	0.3	—	600	—	16.16
		840	—	—	—	—	840	20.29
3b	400	—	—	—	—	360	—	—
	600	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	600	21.14	90.28
		840	—	—	—	—	840	82.01
3c	400	—	—	0.4	—	360	—	—
	600	0.3	—	0.6	—	600	10.99	34.88
		840	—	—	—	—	840	21.53
5a	400	0.1	—	0.2	—	360	—	—
	600	0.3	0.1	0.4	—	600	23.23	31.17
		840	—	—	—	—	840	33.33
5b	400	0.1	0.2	—	—	360	—	—
	600	0.2	0.4	0.1	—	600	20.09	35.60
		840	—	—	—	—	840	39.96
5c	400	0.1	—	0.1	—	360	—	—
	600	0.2	0.3	0.3	—	600	—	29.29
		840	—	—	—	—	840	29.28

is assigned to C-7 to C-10 protons. Another singlet at δ 7.4 is due to the C-5 and C-12 protons.

The molecular ion peaks for the compounds **3** are strong but those for **5** are not that strong, possibly because the dihydro compound may not be so stable¹⁵ at the heated inlet of the mass spectrometer. The major fragments for **3d** appeared at m/z 325 (M^+ , 15%), 310 (15%), 297 (100%), 269 (20%), 192 (25%) and 166 (33%). The important peaks for **5b** appeared at m/z 344 (M^+ , 10%), 209 (100%), 193 (15%), 167, 166 (75%). The peaks of minor importance are ignored.

A perusal of Table 2 reveals that almost all the compounds are ineffective against *P. vulgaris* (-), and moderately active against *B. subtilis* (+) and *S. aureus* (+). All the compounds tested were active against the fungi employed. Compounds **3b** and **5b** were more toxic than the others. Compounds **3c** and **5a** registered 60% inhibition at different dose levels.

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Synthesis of Newer 5-Chloro-2-phenylbenzimidazoles as Potential Antiviral Agents. Part-LIII

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VARIOUS benzimidazoles have been reported to possess antibacterial¹⁻³, antiviral⁴ and anthelmintic⁵ activities. These observations encouraged us to synthesise the title compounds and to screen them for antiviral activity.

2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-chlorobenzimidazole (**1**) was synthesised by the reaction of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine⁶ and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid in presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid⁷. **1** was treated with ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate to yield ethyl-*p*-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxy acetate (**2**), which when further subjected to hydrazinolysis furnished *p*-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxyacetylhydrazine (**3**). **3** was refluxed with isatins and aromatic aldehydes to furnish 3-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)-phenoxyacetylhydrazono]-2-indolinones (**4**) and *N*-(benzylidene)-*p*-[2'-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxyacetylhydrazine (**5**).

The pmr spectrum of **5b** was in accord with the assigned structure, δ 3.87 (3H, OCH_3), 4.82 (2H, $\text{OCH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$), 6.8-8 (14H, NH, =CH and ArH); m/z 434/436 (M^+), 433/435 ($M-1$), 300/302, 243/245, 134, 133, 107, 102, 92 and 64.

Antiviral activity: Compounds **4** and **5** were screened for their antiviral activity against sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV) using the host *C. tetragonoloba* and tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) using the host *Datura stramonium* both *in vitro* and